

Recently Recognized Breeds of Goat in India

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Introduction

In India, total livestock population is 535.78 million among that of India's goat population has been analyzed it has 148.88 million goats, India holds the largest goat population in the world. Over 70 per cent of its people are engaged in vocations connected with farming and animal husbandry. Projections indicate that this number will rise to 162.32 million by 2031. Four states - Rajasthan, West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, and Bihar - account for 43.27% of the country's total goat population. Rajasthan's Barmer district has the largest goat population (2.947 million), followed by Murshidabad in West Bengal (1.751 million), Jodhpur in Rajasthan (1.641 million), and Maldah in West Bengal (1.376 million). The Black Bengal breed has the largest population (17.409 million), followed by Marwari (5.348 million), Osmanabadi (2.481 million), and Barbari (2.194 million) (Livestock census, 2019). Although the overall goat population declined by 3.82% between 2007 and 2012, the population of registered breeds dropped at a significantly higher rate (21.7%) during the same period. Therefore, urgent conservation and improvement measures are necessary to prevent further decline and enhance the productivity of recognized goat breeds.

Goats are versatile animals and an underutilized source of meat, possessing traits that

make them well-suited for sustainable red meat production. They exhibit remarkable adaptability to harsh environments in terms of productivity, reproduction, and disease resistance. For instance, goats can endure heat stress, survive extended periods without water, and thrive in areas with limited land availability. They are also more efficient when raised alongside other ruminants, as they function as both grazers and browsers. Their ability to consume grasses and woody plants that other ruminants avoid makes them an excellent choice for diversified farming. During 2018–19, goats contributed 1.098 million tonnes of meat and 6.099 million tonnes of milk. Various new breeds have been recognized by ICAR-NBAGR in the last five years (Table 1).

Table 1. List of the new registered breeds of Goat

S. No.	Breed	Home Tract	Year of Registration	Accession number
1	Sojat	Rajasthan	2022	INDIA GOAT 1700 SOJAT 06035
2	Karauli	Rajasthan	2022	INDIA_GOAT_1700_KARAULI_06036
3	Gujari	Rajasthan	2022	INDIA_GOAT_1700_GUJARI_06037
4	Anjori	Chhattisgarh	2023	INDIA_GOAT_2600_ANJORI_06038

5	Andamani	Andaman & Nicobar	2023	INDIA_GOAT_3300_ANDAMANI_06039
6	Chaugarkha	Uttarakhand	2025	INDIA_GOAT_2400_CHAUGARKHA_06040
7	Bundelkhandi	Uttar Pradesh	2025	INDIA_GOAT_2010_BUNDELKHANDI_06041

1. Sojat

❖ Origin:

The Sojat goat gets its name from Sojat, a town in Rajasthan's Pali district, where it has been selectively bred and nurtured for generations. Over time, the Sojat goat has been developed through selective breeding to improve meat yield and adaptability to the semi-arid and arid landscapes of western India. Breeders have prioritized traits such as a robust build, broad chest, sturdy legs, and a well-muscled frame, all of which enhance its meat-producing potential.

❖ Physical Characteristics:

- **Body weight:** Adult male Sojat goats typically weigh around 83 kg, while females generally reach 62 kg.
- **Body length:** Males have an overall body length of approximately 36 inches, whereas females measure around 35 inches
- **Sexual maturity:** Males (bucks) reach maturity for breeding at around 8 to 12 months, while females (does) are ready at approximately 10 to 12 months.
- **Identification:**
 - **Coat:** Sojat goats are predominantly white, though some varieties exhibit black or brown patches.
 - **Ear:** They have long, flat, drooping ears, and most males and females possess short, thin tails and are naturally hornless.

[Sojat]

❖ Economical Characteristics:

- The breed is not suited for producing profitable milk. Their average milk production is 271 kg per lactation period and 991 grams per day. The average fat is 3.29 percent and the average SNF is 8.27 percent.

2. Karauli

❖ Origin:

- The Karauli goat is a medium to large-sized breed raised for both meat and milk production. It is primarily found in the districts of Sawai Madhopur, Kota, Bundi, and Baran in Rajasthan. Its most distinctive feature is its medium-sized, corkscrew-shaped horns that point upward.

❖ Physical Characteristics:

- **Weight:** Adult males typically weigh around 52 kg. while females average 45 kg.
- **Sexual maturity:** between 8 to 12 months.
- **Identification mark:**
 - **Coat color:** The Karauli goat exhibits a distinctive coat pattern, predominantly black with brown stripes on the face, ears, abdomen, legs, and near the pin bones
 - **Ear:** Its long, pendulous ears have a folded structure with brown lines along the edges.
 - **Nose:** A notable characteristic of this breed is its Roman nose.
 - **Horn:** The horns are medium-sized, corkscrew-shaped, and point upwards, making them one of the breed's most recognizable features

- **Dewlap:** Karauli bucks also possess a prominent hanging dewlap.

[Karauli]

❖ **Economical Characteristics:**

- The breed performs well in milk production, with an average daily milk yield of 1530.43 ± 19.61 grams and a total lactation yield of 270.04 ± 2.24 kg over a lactation period of approximately 251.70 ± 6.53 days.

3. Gujari

❖ **Origin:**

- The Gujari goat is a large, dual-purpose breed native to Rajasthan, distributed mainly in Jaipur and Sikar districts of Rajasthan. This breed is well-adapted to the hot and arid climate.

❖ **Physical Characteristics:**

- **Body weight:** Adult males typically weigh around 69 kg, while females average 58 kg.
- **Coat colour and pattern:** Its coat features a blend of brown and white, with a predominantly white face, legs, and abdomen.
- **Identification:**
 - **Ear and horn:** The goat has long, pendulous, and folded ears, while its horns are small, twisted, and curve backward.
 - **Beard:** Males typically have a beard, whereas adult females lack one entirely. Most animals of this breed also possess a dewlap.

❖ **Economical Characteristics:**

- The Gujari goat is known for its excellent milk production, with an average daily milk yield of approximately 1616.47 ± 11.45 grams and a total lactation yield of 347.54 ± 2.24 kg over a lactation period of around 250.46 ± 0.95 days.

4. Anjori

❖ **Origin:**

- The Anjori goat is an indigenous breed from Chhattisgarh, India, primarily found in the districts of Raipur, Durg, Rajnandgaon, Kanker, Dhamtari, and Mahasamund.

❖ **Physical Characteristics:**

- **Weight:** Adult females typically weigh between 28 kg, while males range from 35 kg.
- **Coat Color:** The majority of Anjori goats exhibit a brown coat color.

❖ **Economical Characteristics:**

- The breed is well-suited for meat production, with an average market weight of 28–35 kg at 6–9 months and a dressing percentage ranging from 42% to 50% of the total body weight.
- The breed has a daily milk yield of 1.5–2 liters, with a total milk production of 28–30 liters over a lactation period of 120 to 150 days.

[Andamani]

[Anjori]

5. Andamani

❖ Origin:

- Primarily distributed across the Andaman group of islands, with approximately 80% of the population found in the North, Middle, and South Andaman districts.

❖ Physical Characteristics:

- **Body weight:** average body weight of male 19-20 kg and female 17-18 kg
- **Sexual Maturity:** 6-8 month
- **Coat Color:** Predominantly black, with combinations of brown and white also observed.
- **Ears:** Flat, leaf-like, medium-sized, and drooping.
- **Horns:** Both sexes possess small horns that curve upward and backward.
- **Tail:** Medium in length and curves upward.
- **Muzzle:** Color ranges from grey to light black.

❖ Economical Characteristics:

- The breed's milk production ranges from 380 to 750 ml per day, with a lactation period typically lasting between 45 and 90 days.
- The estimated carcass weight is approximately 5.6 to 9.5 kg, accounting for 40–50% of the total body weight, with a live weight ranging from 14 to 19 kg.

6. Chaugarkha

❖ Origin:

- The Chaugarkha goat, also known as Pahadi Bakari (Hill Goat), is a breed native to the Almora district in the Central Himalayas. Its name is derived from the Chaugarkha Patti region.

❖ Physical Characteristics:

- **Sexual maturity:** between 10 to 12 months
- **Herd size:** Most farmers keep herds ranging from 8 to 12 animals
- **Body weight:** Adult females typically weigh between 10 to 12 kg, while males range from 15 to 20 kg.
- **Identification:**
 - **Coat:** Chaugarkha goats are small in size with a lean body, exhibiting coat colors of black, fawn, and white.
 - **Head:** They have a small head with a medium to short forehead, a tapering muzzle, and a distinctive Roman nose.
 - **Ear:** Their ears are medium-sized and positioned horizontally.
 - **Horns:** Both males and females possess straight horns that range in color from ash gray to gray.

❖ Economical Characteristics:

- The first kidding occurs at approximately 16 to 18 months of age.
- These goats are primarily raised for meat, with an average market weight of 20–25 kg at 6–9 months of age and a dressing percentage of 50–55% of the total body weight.
- The breed produces 0.5–1.5 liters of milk per day, with a total milk yield of 60–200 liters over a lactation period of 120–150 days.

7. Bundelkhandi

❖ Origin:

- The purest form of Bundelkhandi goats has been observed in Datia of Madhya Pradesh and Jhansi districts of Uttar Pradesh. Mostly reared by rural farmers and nomadic shepherds for meat and milk production. It is locally known as "Mata-Ka-Bakra,"

❖ Physical Characteristics:

- **Body Weight:** Adult females typically weigh between 30 to 40 kg, while males range from 35 to 45 kg.
- **Sexual Maturity:** Between 8 to 12 month
- **Identification:**
 - **Coat:** They typically have a jet-black coat with black eyelids and muzzle, complemented by grey horns and hooves.
 - **Ears:** Their ears are medium-sized, tubular, and drooping, although some goats display long, ribbon-like pendulous ears.
 - **Head:** A well-proportioned head, a slender face, and a distinct Roman-shaped nose.
 - **Horns:** Their horns generally curve upward and slightly outward, with some individuals exhibiting a screw-like horn structure.
 - **Tail:** The tail is bushy, and certain goats have long hair on their bodies and thighs.

❖ Economical Characteristics:

- The breed is well-suited for meat production, with an average market weight of 25–35 kg at 6–9 months and a dressing percentage of 50–55% of the total body weight.
- The breed has a daily milk yield of 0.5–1.5 liters, with a total lactation yield of 60–200 liters over a period of 120–150 days.

[Bundelkhandi-Male]

[Bundelkhandi - Female]

